

Ultrafast Ce-Mg codoped GAGG garnet single crystal fibers grown by micro-pulling down (μ -PD) technique

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Abstract

We demonstrate the potential of magnesium (Mg^{2+}) co-doping in Ce^{3+} -doped gadolinium aluminum gallium garnet $Gd_3(Ga_3Al_2)O_{12}$ (GAGG:Ce) scintillating crystals to obtain a fast decay time performance and the feasibility of μ -PD technique for growing GAGG:Ce,Mg with high dopant concentrations. We demonstrate that Mg^{2+} co-doping can enhance scintillation kinetics through compositional engineering. An ultra-fast effective decay time of ~ 1 ns was achieved with 2500 ppm Ce and 500 ppm Mg, suggesting that Mg^{2+} co-doping modulates energy transfer pathways through Ce^{3+}/Ce^{4+} activator ions effectively. These results pave the way for the development of ultrafast scintillator materials.

1. Introduction

The next generation of high-energy physics infrastructure such as calorimeters for High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider [1] requires high performance scintillating materials, which constitute an important issue.

The key parameter of calorimeters is their precision and most of the research performed in this field aims at improving material design and energy detection. The $Gd_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)O_{12}$ Garnet (GAGG) appeared to be a good candidate as host material [2] because it combines a high density (high stopping power), and good doping capabilities (fast and intense scintillation). Furthermore, this material exhibits favorable mechanical and chemical properties for crystal growth.

The GAGG:Ce crystals are characterized by a high density (6.63) and high effective atomic number ($Z_{\text{eff}}=54$). They boast a suite of desirable attributes including high light yield (up to 50000 Phot/MeV), a fast decay time of 0.7 ns (the fastest to date), and good energy resolution of up to 6.8 % [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Developing scintillating

crystals with superior timing performance and radiation hardness requires controlling the composition, including co-doping with specific activator ions. One promising approach is to incorporate magnesium (Mg^{2+}), as a co-activator in cerium-doped gadolinium aluminum gallium garnet crystal [8, 9]. The properties of the GAGG crystal vary significantly as a function of the chemical composition and dopants concentration [3]. The incorporation of Mg^{2+} ions alters the crystal field surrounding the Ce activator ions, resulting in modification to the energy transfer pathways and a subsequent reduction in decay time [10]. In addition to the timing performance enhancements, the impact of Mg^{2+} co-doping on the radiation tolerance of GAGG:Ce scintillators is noteworthy. Previous work [9] has demonstrated that GAGG:Ce crystals co-doped with Mg^{2+} (GAGG:Ce,Mg), have improved radiation hardness, rendering them suitable for applications involving intense radiation.

The relatively large ionic radius of the Gd^{3+} host ion in the garnet-type GAGG:Ce, Mg crystal facilitates the incorporation of a high concentration of cerium dopant (up to ~ 1 at.%) and a Mg^{2+} co-dopant (up to ~ 0.5 at.%), without compromising the crystallographic structure or crystal quality [11]. Often, the addition of dopants affects scintillation parameters and crystal properties. To obtain high-quality GAGG:Ce crystals, it is necessary to control the composition and master the growth process in order to eliminate structural inhomogeneities and achieve high performance and controlled mass production. Growing GAGG:Ce,Mg bulk crystals using the Czochralski method has a positive effect on Mg codoping. The decay time (τ_{eff}) has been optimised to 0.7 ns [10, 11, 12, 13]. Unfortunately, the growth process of Ga-containing garnets remains complex due to continued changes in composition relating to Ga_2O_3 losses and liquid Ga depletion during heating and growth operations. A parallel study of the phase of GAGG:Ce ceramics confirmed a reduction in luminescence decay time to 31 ns, associated with $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ transformations, by introducing divalent impurities [14]. In this work, we present the growth of a GAGG:Ce,Mg crystal in a specific shape using the micro pulling down (μ -PD) technique, as well as the impact of Ce and Mg codoping on growth stability and fast decay time.

2. Experimental

2.1. Solid-state synthesis

The host composition selected for this study was $\text{Gd}_3(\text{Ga}_3\text{Al}_2)\text{O}_{12}$. The weight of dopant oxides was meticulously calculated in relation to the gadolinium substitution by dopants $(\text{Gd}_{1-x-y},\text{Ce}_x,\text{Mg}_y)_3(\text{Ga}_3\text{Al}_2)\text{O}_{12}$. (Table 1.). High-purity raw materials were used: Al_2O_3 (99,99%); MgO (99.95%), CeO_2 (99,995%), Gd_2O_3 (99,99%), Ga_2O_3 (99,99%). To compensate gallium losses during the heating and growth operations, an excess of 0.01 wt% Ga (relative to the weight of Ga-oxide) was added in each composition. The initial oxides after thorough mixing and isostatic compression, underwent thermal treatment in air atmosphere under varying conditions. The first cohort of pellets was subjected to annealing at 1200 °C, followed by a subsequent treatment at 1350 °C for 12 hours to enhance the solid-state reaction to obtain GAGG:Ce,Mg single phase.

After annealing (T_{an}) at 1350 °C, visual color transformation from white to yellowish was observed in several pellets, in good agreement with the literature [15]. Under ultraviolet illumination at 365 nm, the intensity of green color luminescence was notably decreased at Mg concentrations from 500 to 1000 ppm.

Table 1. Compositions of GAGG:Ce,Mg presented in our work.

Dopants concentrations	Composition
Ce 1500 ppm/ Mg 0 ppm	$Gd_{2.955}Ce_{0.045}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$
Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 500 ppm	$Gd_{2.94}Ce_{0.045}Mg_{0.015}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$
Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 750 ppm	$Gd_{2.9325}Ce_{0.045}Mg_{0.0225}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$
Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 1000 ppm	$Gd_{2.925}Ce_{0.045}Mg_{0.03}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$
Ce 2000 ppm / Mg 500 ppm	$Gd_{2.925}Ce_{0.06}Mg_{0.015}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$
Ce 2500 ppm / Mg 500 ppm	$Gd_{2.91}Ce_{0.075}Mg_{0.015}Ga_3Al_2O_{12}$

2.2. Fiber crystal growth by μ -PD technique

The GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers were grown by the μ -PD technique [16] using an RF-heated Ir crucible with capillary die of diameter 2.08 mm. The GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers with 1x1 mm cross-section and YAG:Ce fiber of 2.2 mm in diameter were used as seeds. Both seeds were oriented along [111] crystallographic direction. During the first attempts at seeding to available thin GAGG:Ce,Mg the first ~6 cm was grown with a smaller diameter (starting from 1 mm), and with further heat dissipation improvement, after ~6 cm, the diameter was stabilized (to 1.9 mm). With this relation, the seed was changed to another available garnet YAG fiber with dimensions fitting the capillary die (diameter of 2.2 mm) and creating a wider square of the crystallization interface at seeding. In this way, the diameter was controlled from the beginning of the growth in frames of 1.9-2 mm. There was no significant difference in the results due to the relatively high meniscus height during the pulling operation. The meniscus height was precisely maintained within the range of 0.01 mm to 0.06 mm. The resultant fibers exhibited lengths ranging from 50 mm to 110 mm. All fibers underwent cutting (beginning, middle and end part) and polishing procedures in preparation for subsequent examinations. The 2 mm long segments cut from the fibers starting, middle, and tail parts of the fibers were examined by an optical Leica Leitz DMRM Microscope 301-371.010. Concurrently, 5 mm long samples were allocated for the lifetime measurements and samples for optical characterization were polished to 0.8 mm.

Pieces of the grown fibers were crushed and ground into powders in a mortar for room-temperature X-ray diffraction patterns definition by using a Bruker D8 advanced diffractometer with Cu-K α 1 and Cu-K α 2 X-rays ($\lambda = 0.15406$ and 0.15444 nm).

2.3. Optical characterization

Radioluminescence measurements were performed on a homemade setup comprising, as an excitation source, a Mini-X2 X-Ray Tube from Ametek operating at 50kV and 200 μ A, without any filtering. The samples are placed at 2 cm distance from the source exit inside a diffusing liquid scintillation vial, 1 cm in diameter (6 mL Pico Prias Vial from REVITY). This geometrical configuration enables a homogenization of both the

excitation and the emission, making the spectra almost comparable (by weight). The emission is collected by a collimator (thorlabs CVH100-COL) and fed into an optical fiber connected to an ANDOR Shamrock 500 monochromator equipped with a cooled ANDOR Newton 970 EMCCD camera.

Absorption spectra were registered between 300 nm and 2400 nm by using a standard PerkinElmer (PE) double-beam Lambda 900 UV/VIS/ NIR spectrophotometer.

The scintillation emission kinetics was measured in CERN using a Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) setup described in [17]. A pulse diode laser (PicoQuant (LDH-P-C-405) with driver PDL 800-B) was used as an excitation source of an X-ray tube XRT N5084 from Hamamatsu. It generated an X-rays beam with a continuous energy spectrum between 0 and 40 keV (10 keV mean energy). The beam was collimated on the tested sample and its scintillation light was collected by a hybrid photomultiplier (HPM 100-07 Becker Hickl) working in TCSPC mode. A 420 nm long pass filter was placed in front of the hybrid photomultiplier to suppress air excitation contribution to the emission distributions. The measurements were done hitting the sample on one surface and detecting the emitted light from the same surface. The signal of the hybrid PMT reached an amplifier and timing discriminator and was then used as the stop signal of a time to digital converter, while the start was provided by an external trigger of the pulse diode laser.

Each scintillation pulse obtained for the samples from was modeled as:

$$f(t | \theta) = \sum_{i=1}^{N=3} R_i \cdot \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_{d,i}}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_r}\right)}{\tau_{d,i} - \tau_r} \cdot \Theta(t - \theta) + \text{bkg}$$

$\tau_{r,i}$ and $\tau_{d,i}$ are the i -th components of the rise and decay time constants respectively, R_i is the weight of the i -th component, θ is the instant above which the scintillation pulse starts and bkg is the background. The scintillation pulse function defined above was then convoluted with the impulse response function (IRF) of the setup (~ 180 ps FWHM) to fit the emission distributions obtained. Rise times below 30 ps are comparable with the experimental precision and with the resolution of the setup. From the decay time constants obtained and their weight, the effective decay time of the sample can be evaluated as follows:

$$\tau_{d,\text{eff}} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N=3} \frac{R_i}{\tau_{d,i}} \right)^{-1}$$

where N is the number of components employed for the fit. In our analysis we used 3 components (section 3.4).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. Fibers crystal growth

A series of GAGG:Ce, Mg fibres were successfully grown by the micro-pulling down technique (Fig. 1a) regardless of the concentration of Ce and Mg dopants. A progressive color shift was observed: to yellowish hues with increasing Ce concentration, and to greenish hues with increasing Mg concentration, when exposed to daylight and a UV lamp (365 nm) (Fig. 1b). Most crystals appear slightly cloudy due to their rough surface. However, the inner part of all the crystals is completely transparent. The fiber with Ce at 1500 ppm and Mg at 500 ppm demonstrated the best quality (Fig. 2). Strong layers of bubbles and cracks were observed near the periphery of the grown fibres with Ce concentrations of 1500–2500 ppm and Mg concentrations of 500–1000 ppm. The bubbles are distributed at a distance of 10–30 μm from the edge of the rods (dark region near the periphery). They are distributed irregularly within the rods. On the surface of the crystal, they are located at the periphery. However, sometimes the bubbles are found in the center of the crystal. When the bubbles concentration becomes high enough, the bubble can nucleate. Afterward, the bubbles grow and move, and they can be attracted and incorporated into the crystal, or they will remain in the liquid, being rejected by the solidification interface. So, it is possible to concentrate the bubbles very close to the surface of the rods (figure 5), from where it is relatively easy to remove them by polishing. In this case, it is crucial to know what the useful thickness is or, in other words, what is the distance between the bubble curtain and the edge of the crystal. Following our results and until proven otherwise, bubbles are formed by the incorporation of impure liquid which creates cavities as it cools. The impurities that cause this effect may be those dissolved in the raw material, or those added as doping (Ce and Mg dopants), or gases (Argon) from the growth atmosphere that have a segregation coefficient less than unity ($k < 1$).

The growth of the stoichiometric GAGG:Ce,Mg compound without the excess of Ga_2O_3 results in the continuous evaporation of gallium oxide, enriching the melt with Gd_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 which act as fluxes. It is important to note that the process of Gd_2O_3 melt impoverishment is irreversible. Once the melt becomes Ga-poor, it is impossible to maintain consistent melt properties such as the crystallisation temperature and subsequent meniscus shape. However, minor fractions of CeO_2 and MgO were also detected in the XRD diagram.

Figure 1: Photos of the grown GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers at daylight (a) with a corresponding photo of samples cut from each fiber exposed to 365 nm excitation. The variations in Ce/Mg content variations are indicated in figure (b). Note the decrease in luminescence intensity at lower Ce and higher Mg concentrations and the shift to a green hue with an increase in Mg content.

All the fibers contain specific imperfections, including bubbles and cracks, which can be seen under optical microscopy (Fig. 2). These defects may originate from various sources, such as stoichiometric shifts in the ternary equilibrium diagram ($\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) due to gallium oxide volatilization during melt overheating, or variations in growth conditions, such as thermal gradient fluctuations.

Essentially, the peripheral ring of bubbles is related to convection in the melt and the capture of gas at the crystallization interface [18, 19]. However, if the pulling rate is low ($v \leq 0.3$ mm/min), the gas bubbles have time to be rejected from the meniscus back to the growth atmosphere due to the vortices in the meniscus, which is in good agreement with our previous work [20, 21].

Higher pulling rates ($v > 0.3$ mm/min) resulted in a significant reduction in diameter (0.3 mm/min ($\varnothing \approx 1.6$ mm); 0.5 mm/min ($\varnothing \approx 1.1$ mm); 0.7 mm/min ($\varnothing \approx 0.9$ mm)), as evidenced by the growth of fiber containing 1500 ppm Ce and 1000 ppm Mg. The meniscus height increased by 0.1 mm, presumably due to composition evolution in the Gd_2O_3 - Ga_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 equilibrium diagram, resulting from melt overheating and subsequent Ga_2O_3 evaporation, which was deposited on the internal surface of the alumina ceramic thermal insulation.

The fast growth rates led to a deterioration in fiber quality, with the propagation of bubbles and cracks due to strong thermal stress, which is in good agreement with our previous work [18, 22]. Rings of bubbles appeared at the peripheral edge of the fibres, causing transparency to degrade. The only way to prevent the formation of bubbles was to decrease the pulling rate ($v \leq 0.3$ mm/min), which is consistent with our previous work [18, 22]. In cases of melt overheating, the fiber disconnection was obviously due to an increase in meniscus height, which caused a significant reduction in fiber diameter. This was followed by fiber separation from the melting zone. This disconnection is connected to continued composition evolution in the ternary equilibrium diagram due to the shift in composition from the congruent point, in agreement with our previous work on langatate (LGT) containing Ga_2O_3 [23, 24]. A stationary, stable growth state corresponds to a meniscus height range of [0.03–0.06 mm], enabling stable fiber pulling. The fiber diameter varied from 1.8 to 1.95 mm for a Ce concentration of 1500–2500 ppm and a Mg concentration of 500–1000 ppm. The fiber with a Ce concentration of 1500 ppm and a Mg concentration of 500 ppm demonstrated the best quality (Fig. 5). Strong layers of bubbles and cracks were observed near the periphery of the grown fibres with Ce concentrations of 1500–2500 ppm and Mg concentrations of 500–1000 ppm.

Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 0 ppm

Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 500 ppm

Ce 2000 ppm / Mg 500 ppm

Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 750 ppm

Ce 2500 ppm / Mg 500 ppm

Ce 1500 ppm / Mg 1000 ppm

Figure 2. Transverse cut view of the GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers as a function of dopant concentration

3.2. XRD analysis

Figure 3 shows the room temperature X-ray diffraction pattern analysis of GAGG:Ce,Mg as a function of Ce dopant concentration, alongside the reference pattern of Ce_{0.015}Gd_{2.985}Al₂Ga₃O₁₂ (PDF 04-023-5738). Regardless of the position of the analysed fibre (top, beginning or end), all compositions correspond to the cubic (Ia3d) garnet GAGG:Ce,Mg phase, with no secondary phases present. The structure consists of three cation sites: dodecahedral, octahedral and tetrahedral. The eightfold-coordinated dodecahedral sites are occupied by Gd³⁺ ions, whereas the sixfold- or fourfold-coordinated octahedral or tetrahedral sites are occupied by both Al³⁺ and Ga³⁺ ions [25]. In GAGG:Ce,Mg, Ce is the only multiple-valence element with (3+) and (4+) valences. The addition of the bivalent Mg²⁺ ion is thought to create crystal defects that generate localised energy levels within the band gap of the garnet structure [2].

Figure 3. Room temperature XRD patterns of GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers as a function of dopants concentration.

Analysis of the material deposited on the thermal insulation ceramics (see Fig. 4.) revealed the expected presence of Ga₂O₃ oxide. However, minor fractions of CeO₂ and MgO were also detected, suggesting that volatile Ga₂O₃ entrains CeO₂ and MgO from the melt during GAGG decomposition during the heating process (Fig.4a).

Figure 4: (a) The deposit on the thermal insulation and (b) the room temperature XRD pattern of the powder deposited on the heat insulation during growth

3.3. Radioluminescence and absorption

It is observed that the intensity of radioluminescence decreases with the addition of magnesium (from 0 to 1000 ppm) and increases further (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5c). This effect is associated with the formation of Ce⁴⁺ ions in the GAGG:Ce crystal lattice during co-doping with Mg (see references [8, 10, 12]). This is confirmed by an increase in absorption intensity in the 350 nm region (Fig. 6), which corresponds to charge transfer (CT) absorption of the O₂—Ce⁴⁺ complex [10]. We assume that the compositions implemented in the work with the extremities of the dopant concentrations (Ce 2500 ppm, Fig. 5b and Mg 1000 ppm, Fig. 5c) are the limit for GAGG crystals, as the scintillation intensity decreases significantly. Further investigation is required into the requirements for fast-timing luminescence garnets, particularly with regard to the trade-off between scintillation decay time and light output.

Figure 5. Radioluminescence spectra of GAGG:Ce,Mg samples (a), intensity of radioluminescence regarding the concentrations of codopants Ce (b) and Mg (c)

Figure 6. Absorption spectra of GAGG:Ce,Mg samples as a function of Ce, Mg dopant concentration

3.4. Decay time

Figure 7 illustrates the principle of TCSPC measurements on a single GAGG fibre. Figure 8 shows the scintillation decay time spectra for six GAGG fibres as a function of dopant concentration, with excitation by picosecond X-ray pulses. The fibers differ in their dopant composition, specifically their Ce and Mg content (see legend). As can be seen, the absence of Mg results in markedly slower scintillation kinetics and a pronounced long tail. In contrast, fibers with high Ce concentrations and added Mg exhibit the fastest decay. These spectra demonstrate the trade-off between dopant levels and scintillation speed.

Figure 7. : Illustration of a TCSPC measurement of a GAGG fiber. This is an example of typical obtained data and corresponding fits. The blue dots represent the measured entries, the green solid line is a moving average of these points, and the red solid line shows the fitting curve. The plot is on a logarithmic scale; the bottom panel shows the residuals of the fit.”

Figure 8. Scintillation decay time spectra of all the GAGG fibers at excitation by picosecond X-ray pulses.

Scintillation emission quenching and correlated acceleration of the effective lifetime (τ_{eff}) were observed as the Mg concentration in the GAGG:Ce, Mg samples increased (Fig. 9). The decay times of all the grown fibers were very close to those of the fastest previously reported bulk crystals [10]. At a constant Mg concentration of 500 ppm, the decay time decreased with increasing Ce concentrations. When the Mg concentration was increased (to 500, 750 and 1000 ppm, respectively), the decay time remained at a similar level for identical Ce concentrations (1500 ppm). The defects observed under microscopy had no significant effect on the decay time and can be disregarded. Considering the optical and scintillation parameters discussed in the paper, the compositions with Ce 1500–2000 ppm and Mg 500–750 ppm are suggested as the best candidates among the grown fibers. The fibers were uniform from beginning to end compared to the results reported for Cz-grown bulk crystals [10]. Codoping was beneficial for the decay time compared to Mg-free fibre (44 ns), improving it by a factor of 20 for all grown GAGG:Ce,Mg fibres. Table 2 presents our decay time results in comparison to some references [3, 10]. The fastest effective decay time (τ_{eff}) of 0.61 ns was achieved in GAGG with 2500 ppm Ce and 500 ppm Mg at the beginning of the fiber; this increased to 1.9 ns at the tail (end) of the fiber. The same trend of increasing decay time in the tails was observed in all the fibers and, until proven otherwise, this can be attributed to reabsorption phenomena at high Ce concentrations in the tails due to the phenomenon of dopant segregation.

Figure 9. τ_{eff} in GAGG:Ce,Mg samples in dependence of Ce, Mg dopant

Table 2. Decay times of GAGG:Ce,Mg compared to our grown crystals. The most efficient and promising results among the grown compositions are underlined.

Previously reported results on the fastest GAGG:Ce,Mg from different references				
τ_{eff} (ns)			Reference	
57			[3]	
0.7			[10]	
Results on GAGG:Ce,Mg in our work				
τ_{eff} (ns)			Concentration of Ce (ppm)	Concentration of Mg (ppm)
Beginnings	Middles	Tails		
<u>1.4</u>	<u>2.4</u>	<u>2.1</u>	<u>1500</u>	<u>750</u>
1.1	1.7	1.8	1500	1000
<u>1.3</u>	<u>1.3</u>	<u>2.2</u>	<u>1500</u>	<u>500</u>
<u>1.2</u>	<u>1.1</u>	<u>1.9</u>	<u>2000</u>	<u>500</u>
0.6	1.1	1.9	2500	500

4. Conclusions

Using the μ -PD technique, we succeeded in growing GAGG:Ce,Mg scintillating fibers and demonstrated that a concentration range of 1500–2500 ppm of activator (Ce), coupled with a concentration range of 500–1000 ppm of co-dopant (Mg), yields GAGG:Ce,Mg fibers with very fast decay times of 0.6–2.4 ns.

The influence of the Mg co-dopant on crystal growth and structural homogeneity has been demonstrated. Concentrations of Mg above 500 ppm were found to have a positive impact on the growth stability and transverse homogeneity of the fibers. Remarkably, all GAGG:Ce,Mg fibres exhibited uniformity, and the decay was 20 times faster than that of previous work on bulk crystals grown by the Cz method, which is a crucial factor for the consistent performance of the next generation of high-energy detectors. Incorporating Mg^{2+} ions in GAGG:Ce single-crystal fibers is an effective strategy for achieving faster scintillation kinetics.

Our growth experiments established the optimal parameters for the μ -PD technique. Specifically, a medium meniscus height ranging from 0.03 mm to 0.06 mm yielded successful and reproducible results.

This work has allowed us to use the μ -PD technique to achieve stationary, stable growth of GAGG:Ce,Mg scintillation fibers 50–110 mm long with extremely fast decay times. It has also provided a robust foundation for future advancements in crystal growth techniques and decay time optimisation.

Author contributions

V.K.: Crystal growth, characterization and writing paper.

P.M.: Characterization, advices and results discussion.

A.N.: Crystal growth advices, advices in management of works and results discussion.

C.D.: Advises in characterization, results discussion and participation in paper reading.

L.R.: Characterization, results discussion and participation in paper editing

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

All the data supporting this work have been included within the article and is available on request.

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